

HARDNESS APPRAISAL OF MEDIUM DENSITY FIBREBOARD (MDF) IN NIGERIAN ECONOMY

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Abstract: Expert knowledge on hardness test analysis on medium density fibreboard (MDF) in Nigerian market needed by stakeholders to avoid loss of finances that may arise due to choice of inappropriate medium density fibreboard (MDF) for plentiful demands as a result of non-availability of such data was investigated. The top three most frequently sought after medium density fibreboard (MDF) were identified and subjected to test to establish their hardness. The samples as required by the Leeds Hardness Tester were prepared and tested four times on the machine and the mean determined. From the generated data, plots on the hardness of the samples were ensued by computer program. Results show that Hokusan attained aggregate average hardness of 535.75 Leeds Hardness Test (HLD), Richard Russel attained aggregate average hardness of 545.75 HLD while SGK Nordiac attained aggregate average hardness of 558.50 HLD. According to statistics, that of SGK Nordiac is 2.34% and 4.25% harder than Richard Russel and Hokusan respectively. The difference in hardness between Richard Russel and Hokusan which is 10 HLD is small compared to the difference in hardness between SGK Nordiac and Hokusan which is as much as 22.75 HLD. Choice of suitable medium density fibreboard based on their hardness would be informed by this novel revelation. Biomedical engineers, engineers as well as other stake holders should utilize these results in their products development. Future research attention should be geared towards hardness tests of high-density fibreboard (HDF) in Nigerian economy.

Keyword: Indentation Testing, Leed Hardness Test, Material Hardness Testing, Material Testing, Mechanical Testing, Rockwell Hardness Test, Scleroscope Testing, Surface Hardness Testing.

I. Introduction

Background of the Study

At a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) estimate of 4.5% as noted by (FMRL, 2025) the global plywood market valued at USD 50.2 billion in 2024 is expected to grow from year 2025 with projection to reach USD 74.5 billion by the year 2033. Extensively used across construction, furniture, and packaging industries in

Nigeria, wood composite remains a vital engineered wood product. Unfortunately, Nigeria presently remains heavily dependent on plywood imports despite abundant raw materials and a fast-growing domestic market. FMRL, (2025) noted that the Nigerian plywood market valued at USD 8.81 billion in 2023 and being on a growth direction is expected to grow at a CAGR of 3.3%, reaching USD 11.05 billion by 2030. Forestry products industrial goods exports in the 1950's, 1960's and 1970's were once enjoyed by Nigeria, (Ogunwusi, 2012). Wood composites, a derivative of wood product are normally obtained through the processes of binding the particles, strands, boards, or fibers of wood together. From vegetable fibers using lignin-containing materials with chemical additives enabling the integration of polymer and wood flour while helping facilitate optimal processing conditions, similar composite products can also be made. Garcia-Garcia, et al, (2018), noted that due to an excellent combination of mechanical, thermal and acoustic properties together with a competitive price usually made of materials like rye and wheat straw, sugar cane residue, hemp stalks e.t.c, particle and fiberboards are widely used in the building industry as eco-friendly solutions to wood with increasing uses in thermal insulators, ceiling boards, wall partitions, e.t.c. Wood composites are engineered to certain specifications resulting in a material that can have diverse applications and this is achieved by the use adhesives. It is of interest to note that wood composites can be created by the use of smaller trees, wood waste materials and hence reduce the need to fell old-growth forests. It is revealing that there is a remarkable improvement of the mechanical properties with combination of the alkali treatment followed by silanization while studying the production of highly environmentally-friendly fiberboards by hot-press molding using *Posidonia oceanica* wastes and a partially biobased epoxy resin as binder, (Garcia-Garcia, et al, 2018). In terms of challenges associated with it as a result of higher chemical heat content and melting properties, higher fire hazards could be experienced when wood composite is compared to solid wood products. Most cheap and common resins usually used in the composites and made with urea-formaldehyde bonded products release toxic formaldehyde in the finished products forming a strong apprehension with wood composite use. Though the process of their manufacture as it relates to solid timber demands for extra primary energy, wood composites have numerous advantages. Worthy of mention also is the humidity-induced warping which is not a common experience in solid woods by some fiber-based and particle based composite woods when they are exposed to moisture. Despite all these challenges stated, it is interesting to note that the demand for wood composite is on the rise as projected by the earlier statistics due to remarkable improvement on esthetic and mechanical properties of the resulting composites. Barguma, et al (2022), observed that the purchasing power of the Nigerian currency Naira in the study of inflation trend pattern and its impact on Nigeria's economy was seen to be decreasing, a revelation that the economy especially building materials market is badly hit by the inflation. Igboekulie, Monye, and Joseph, (2022), assessed the effect of building materials cost on housing development in Owerri, Imo state, eastern region of Nigeria and noted that a very strong relationship has been found to exist between building materials prices and rate of residential development. Obaedo, (2024) while analyzing the inflation rate and the prices of building materials in Benin city, from a correlation analysis, X-rayed inflation as

the most influential factor responsible for increase in the cost of building materials with the prices of the building materials having a direct relationship with the inflation rate in Nigeria thus the cause for the high cost of building materials.

Testing for Material Hardness

Materials hardness testing is any procedure employed to determine a material's resistance to scratching, indentation or even deformation. The test is usually conducted by penetration of another harder material to ascertain the actual resistance exhibited by materials to permanent deformation. By penetration of another harder material, it is simply a test conducted to ascertain the actual resistance exhibited by materials to permanent deformation. Material hardness testing is a mechanical test for material properties which are used in structural analysis, materials development and engineering design and development. By pressing a harder material into the surface of the tested material this is achieved. Indicating how well the material can resist deformation that is permanent the size of the resulting indentation which is basically the depth is measured and subsequently converted into a hardness value. In Brinell Hardness Test, a hardened steel or carbide ball indenter is used to create an indentation on the surface of the material being tested while the Brinell Hardness Number (BHN) is calculated from the measured diameter of the indentation. To provide quick and easy measurement for very soft materials like plastics, Barcol Hardness Test is mainly used. For over a wide range of materials from very soft to very hard ones by the use of a square-based diamond pyramid indenter, Vickers Hardness Test is employed. Knoop Hardness Test uses a rhombic-based diamond pyramid indenter, and is often used for thin films and brittle materials, just like Vickers Hardness Test. Shore Durometer measures the hardness of rubber and plastics with the use of a spring -loaded indenter while the Scleroscope measures hardness by the rebound height of a diamond-tipped hammer that is dropped onto a material. Adopted in this research is Leed Hardness Test a dynamic impact test that measures the rebound of a small impactor (indenter) to determine the hardness (HLD).

II. Literature Review

A linear relationship is found to exist between age and strength properties of timber, increasing both the compression and shear strengths and even to a reasonable extent the bending strength, (Ojo and Idieunmah, 2021). The effect of particle size on the flexural strength, ultimate tensile strength, density and water absorption characteristics of uncarbonized coconut shell/unsaturated polyester composites of particle size 425 microns sample and 170 microns sample were investigated by (Iloabachie, et al, 2017) and the result indicated that maximum flexural and ultimate tensile strength were attained at 20wt% for the 425 microns sample. Comparing the effect of adding a blend of tannins to commercial urea formaldehyde (UF) on the particleboard made from wood particles of *Acacia seyal* var. *seyal* using the British Standard European Norm (BSEN) relevant standards as compared to the ones produced by solely urea formaldehyde (UF), it was revealed that effect was experience of high mechanical properties, (Elbadawi, et al, 2015). Results of mechanical properties tests by (Iloabachie, Obiorah and Anene, (2018) show that flexural strength and elongation at break increased as coconut shell

proportion got increased upon the study of the effects of carbonized coconut shell (CS) volume fraction on mechanical properties of unsaturated polyester resin (UPR) composite. Tensile strength of Teak Wood Saw Dust – Cashew nut shell liquid resin composites was studied by preparing a composite material using a hand layup technique by varying the quantity of the Cashew nut shell liquid (CNSL) resin and keeping the saw dust quantity constant by simple methodology of just increasing the percentage of (CNSL). According to the ASTM D638, tensile strength test on the composites using a Universal Testing Machine (UTM) by (Ganesan and Valarmathi, 2014) revealed that tensile strength of the sample with the highest percentage of (CNSL) was the highest and that the **tensile** increased with increase in (CNSL). Conclusively, the tensile strength of the composite is improved with the increase in the cashew nut shell liquid (CNSL) percentage. Upon the study of performance characteristics and reinforcement combinations of coconut fibre reinforced high density polyethylene (HDPE) polymer matrixes at optimum condition of volume fractions and particle sizes of coconut fibre-filler, (Ihuezze, Achike, and Okafor, 2016) found that coconut fibre reinforced HDPE has 28.6 mega pascal as optimum value for flexural strength. In a study conducted to test for the potentials of low-density polyethylene (LDPE) such as plastic films from packaging as resins for saw dust from coconut lumber for the production of wood-plastic composite (WPC) particleboard when the boards were prepared from 50%-80% by weight of LPDE to sawdust content, both physical and mechanical properties of WPC evaluated, (Valle, 2020) found that the tensile strength, face screw holding and modulus of rupture meet the minimum specifications of the US standards. Good interfacial adhesion between sawdust particle and LDPE reduced thickness swelling and improving moisture resistance by diminishing hygroscopy hence expanding the utilization of composites from agricultural wastes and plastic wastes for industrial applications, especially in moist environments, even as well as marine use and humid environment was also revealed by the study. Following the analysis of the effects of carbonization on the physical and mechanical properties of coconut shell particle reinforced polyester composite, (Iloabachie, et al 2014) revealed that carbonized coconut shell particle reinforced composite recorded the least density value making it desirable in light weight material application. Sequel to evaluation of the properties of developed composite corn cob (CC) and sawdust (SD) particle boards using 100%, 75%, 50%, 25% and 0% variations for both agricultural wastes using formaldehyde as binder at constant volume, (Akinyemi. Afolayan, and Oluwatobi, 2016) found that for both physical and mechanical properties, the panels with 50% CC had the most preferred performances. Analysis on the optimization of hardness strengths response of plantain fibres reinforced polyester matrix composites (PFRP) by application of Taguchi robust design, by (Okafor, Ihuezze, and Nwigbo, 2013) showed that empty fruit bunch fibre reinforced polyester matrix composite has the maximum hardness strength of 19.062 N/mm² which depended greatly on the reinforcement combinations of control factors. From critical evolution of surface properties of concrete through measured lightness and absorption as analysed in the study of panel formworks, (Courard, et al, 2012) noted that changes were observed on surface quality after 50 reuses with oriented strand board (OSB) panels formworks while modification of surface quality was noticed after 80 reuses with marine plywood formworks. Upon the analysis

of the effect of carbonization temperature on wear rate behaviour of rice husk ash reinforced epoxy composites, (Ozioko, 2011) revealed that wear behaviours of 9500C carbonized ash were better than those of 8500C and 9000C carbonized ash due to the degree of alteration in the structure of silica. Upon the assessment of the flexural strength of glued laminated beams made from local wood species bonded with phenol resorcinol formaldehyde, polyurethane and urea-formaldehyde adhesives, (Ekundayo, Arum and Owoyemi, 2022) found that the values in glulam beams are significantly higher than the control (custom wood) especially in edgewise direction.

Clearly, it is certain from the summary of reviewed literature with regards to their hardness that research has not been directed towards providing technical information on hardness of medium density fibreboard (MDF) in Nigerian economy, hence the need for the research in this area.

III. Research Methodology

Material

Investigation was made on commonly used and major medium density fibreboard (MDF) in the Nigerian market. From the survey made, most common and three medium density fibreboard (MDF) in top demands in Nigerian market were identified. They were selected as samples for analysis. The medium density fibreboard (MDF) samples were Richard Russel, SGK Nordiac and Hokusan. They are represented accordingly in table 1. In table 1, the samples are coded “a”, “b” and “c” representing Richard Russel, SGK Nordiac and Hokusan respectively. They are all prepared according to the requirement by the machine and tested on the machine one after the other.

TABLE 1 Medium Density Fibreboard (MDF) Samples Tested

Sample	a	B	c
Make	Richard Russel	SGK Nordiac	Hokusan

Figure 1 shows the materials under investigation as marked in the table 1.

(a) (b) (c)

Fig. 1: Medium Density Fibreboard tested

Equipment

A portable non-destructive machine for measuring hardness, the Leeds hardness tester as seen in figure 2 which is a type of dynamic hardness test machine was used. It works on the rebound velocity of usually a small impact body which is the indenter after it strikes the surface of the material. The indenter is placed on each sample and device gadget clicked; the indenter pushes to make an indent on the sample.

Carefully set according to the requirement by the Leeds hardness tester in figure 2, the samples (a) representing Richard Russel, (b) representing SGK Nordiac and (c) representing Hokusan were all tested on the machine successively. The Leeds hardness tester indenter pushes forward to make an impact on the sample by indenting on it as it is operated by placing the indenter of the Leeds hardness tester on the sample and clicking the control button. For each sample (make), the operation is repeated four times. The dynamics of the action of the indenting and the associated resistance, the Leed hardness (HLD) plots are generated with computer program. The plot which is a function of the sample's composition resulting from their nature shows clearly the relationship between force per unit area and the extent of the impact (indent) in the sample. The plots generated are discussed under results and analysis.

Fig. 2: Leids Hardness Tester.

IV. Results and Analysis

For each of the samples Richard Russel, SGK Nordiac and Hokusan, the results of the tests are shown as plots in figures 3, 4 and 5 respectively. Essentially, the hardness test results in HLD are for the tested samples of the three selected medium density fibreboard (MDF).

Plots

The figure 3 below is a plot for hardness test result of Richard Russel sample. The first test recorded 486 HLD, the second recorded 529 HLD, the third recorded 569 HLD while the fourth recorded 599 HLD. The aggregate average of the four tests is taken and reported in the figure 6 for a comparative analysis.

Fig 3: Graph of Hardness Test Results for Richard Russel in HLD.

The figure 4 below is a plot for hardness test result of SGK Nordiac sample. The first test recorded 585 HLD, the second recorded 561 HLD, the third recorded 536 HLD while the fourth recorded 552 HLD. The aggregate average of the four tests is taken and reported in the figure 6 for a comparative analysis.

Fig. 4: Graph of Hardness Test Results for SGK Nordiac in HLD.

The figure 5 below is a plot for hardness test result of Hokusan sample. The first test recorded 544 HLD, the second recorded 542 HLD, the third recorded 544 HLD while the fourth recorded 513 HLD. The aggregate average of the four tests is taken and reported in the figure 6 for a comparative analysis.

Fig. 5: Graph of Hardness Test Results for Hokusan in HLD.

The figure 6 below is a plot for aggregate average of the four hardness tests result on the samples. Richard Russel recorded 545.75 HLD, SGK Nordiac recorded 558.50 HLD while Hokusan recorded 535.75 HLD.

Fig. 6: Graph of Aggregate Average of Hardness Test Results for Richard Russel, SGK Nordiac and Hokusan in HLD.

V. Conclusion and Recommendation

In an ascending order of their hardness test results, Hokusan achieved aggregate average of hardness test result of 535.75 HLD, Richard Russel achieved aggregate average of hardness test result of 545.75 HLD while SGK Nordiac achieved aggregate average of hardness test result of 558.50 HLD. Comparatively in terms of hardness, SGK Nordiac is 2.34% and 4.25% harder than Richard Russel and Hokusan respectively. Richard Russel is also 1.87% harder than Hokusan. These are typically obtained from the result of the tests. This implies that Richard Russel is harder than Hokusan while SGK Nordiac is harder than Richard Russel. It is worthy to note that the difference in hardness between Richard Russel and Hokusan is small compared to the difference in hardness between SGK Nordiac and Hokusan which is as much as 22.75 HLD. Depending on application, choice of medium density fibreboard (MDF) from Nigeria market can leverage on this novel technical data with respect to their hardness potentials. This Novel specialized knowledge should be valued by architects, building contractors, engineers, individuals, construction companies as well as furniture makers. Developers of biomedical engineering equipment can as well utilise this knowledge. Hardness tests analysis of high-density fibreboard (HDF) in Nigerian market should form future research works in wood composites.

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